

Free Radical-induced Chain Reactions in Solution. Part. II. A Kinetic Investigation of Reduction of Heptavalent Manganese by Oxalate and some Hydroxy-carboxylic Acid Anions Induced by Cobalt(III)

E. M. Kurian and S. Ghosh

The kinetics and mechanism of reduction of heptavalent manganese by oxalate, tartrate, and citrate, induced by the respective organic free radical, have been studied; an autocatalytic rate expression describes the data. Results show that the initial rate-limiting step is an electron-transfer from the organic free radical to permanganate anion, thereby generating the Mn(VI). Kinetic evidence leads to the conclusion that higher-valent manganese, Mn(VI to III), undergoes single-electron transfer with the organic substrate yielding the relevant organic free radical in contrast to a two-electron transfer proposed earlier. Autocatalysis is due to the favoured reaction of Mn(II) with Mn(VII), thereby forming Mn(VI) and Mn(III).

The possibility of the occurrence of a chain reaction involving free radicals as active transient intermediates might be obtained by observing whether the reaction could be induced or accelerated by introduction of free radicals¹. That cobalt(III) in the form of potassium cobaltic carbonate in acid becomes a potent source for some organic free radicals has already been observed². The oxalate, tartrate, and citrate free radicals are produced *in situ* by instantaneous interaction of these organic anions and cobalt(III). The impact of these free radicals on the reduction of permanganate anion has been studied in the present communication as it may reveal the mode of reduction of manganese(VII) to manganese(II) by these organic anions.

EXPERIMENTAL

Chemicals used were of AnalaR or E. Merck Extra pure or G. R. specifications. Potassium permanganate was filtered through sintered-glass crucible before standardisation by the oxalate method. Potassium cobaltic carbonate was prepared by the method of Burdett and Laitinen³. Care was taken to remove the excess hydrogen peroxide; cobalt(III) in the complex was determined iodometrically. Oxalate-oxalic, tartrate-tartronic, and citrate-citric acid mixtures were obtained by putting the requisite quantity of potassium bicarbonate, taking into account the bicarbonate present in the cobalt complex. The initial pHs of such solutions were measured with a Radio pH meter-4 of reproducibility ± 0.001 .

1. E. W. R. Steacie, "Atomic and Free Radical Reactions", Reinhold, New York, 1946, pp. 19-21
2. Kurian and Ghosh, this *Journal*, 1965, **42**, 169.
3. *Anal. Chem.*, 1951, **23**, 1268.

Requisite quantity of the oxidant and the inductor were introduced into a known amount of the reductant and the kinetics was followed by estimating the concentrations of the oxidant iodometrically at definite time lags.

TABLE I

$$\text{Validity of the rate expression } k = \frac{2.303}{(a+b)} \log_{10} \frac{a(b+x)}{b(a-x)}$$

(a). (Oxalic acid) = $2 \times 10^{-2} N$. (KHCO_3) = $1.84 \times 10^{-2} N$. (KMnO_4) = $1 \times 10^{-3} N$. (Co^{III}) = $1 \times 10^{-4} N$.
pH = 4.78. Temp. = 28°.

<i>t</i> (min.)	..	5	10	15	20	25	30	35	40	45	50
<i>k</i> × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹	..	3.22	2.78	2.48	2.27	2.19	2.13	2.11	2.05	2.04	2.02

(b). (Tartaric acid) = $1 \times 10^{-2} N$. (KHCO_3) = $9 \times 10^{-3} N$. (KMnO_4) = $1 \times 10^{-3} N$. (Co^{III}) = $1 \times 10^{-4} N$.
Temp. = 16.5°.

<i>t</i> (min.)	..	5	10	15	20	25	30	35	40	45
<i>k</i> × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹	..	6.85	4.01	3.03	2.52	2.28	2.11	2.00	2.04	2.04

(c). (Citric acid) = $1 \times 10^{-2} N$. (KHCO_3) = $8 \times 10^{-3} N$. (KMnO_4) = $1 \times 10^{-3} N$. (Co^{III}) = $5 \times 10^{-5} N$.
Temp. = 18°.

<i>t</i> (min.)	..	5	15	25	35	45	55	65	75
<i>k</i> × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹	..	11.4	4.22	2.91	2.21	1.86	1.65	1.55	1.50

TABLE II

Dependence of reaction rate on acidity and (Co^{III}) for oxalate.
(Reductant) = $1 \times 10^{-2} N$. (KMnO_4) = $1 \times 10^{-3} N$. Temp. = 28°.

(Co ^{III}).	pH : 4.78	4.40	4.02	3.68
$0.5 \times 10^{-4} N$, <i>k</i> × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹	..	..	1.82	2.43
$1 \times 10^{-4} N$, <i>k</i> × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹	..	1.51	2.48	3.10
$2 \times 10^{-4} N$, <i>k</i> × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹	..	2.01	..	..

The trend is the same for tartrate and citrate.

DISCUSSION

When minute quantities of cobalt (III) in the form of potassium cobaltic carbonate is introduced into the reaction mixture consisting of the reductant and permanganate, the reduction of the latter is immediately initiated. The rate of reduction continues to increase till the purple colour of permanganate gives way to a cherry-red one due to Mn(II) complex which grades into brownish yellow and then to colorless. The rate of reduction of the oxidant does not conform to the usual kinetics. The autocatalytic rate constants, calculated on the basis of the rate expression arrived at from the mechanism advanced subsequently, are higher in the very initial stage, but come to satisfactory constancy and persist so long as the pink colour of permanganate is visible (Tables I and II). Afterwards

the solution was completely of cherry-red colour and reduction proceeded according to first-order law⁴ (data excluded) at various parameters investigated.

The reduction of permanganate by these reductants under identical conditions is accompanied by a long induction period of the order of hours and is very slow in absence of cobalt (III) or (II). The oxidation of oxalate ions by permanganate ions is very slow⁵, if it proceeds at all. In fact, if any manganese (II) be present *in albeit* in permanganate solution, it is oxidised by cobalt (III) to the higher-valent stage quantitatively and hence hardly could any manganese (II) be present in the system prior to its formation. Therefore the initiation of the reduction by

as suggested by Malcolm and Noyes⁵, is not valid here. Cobalt (III) in presence of certain organic substrates has already been shown² to yield immediately the relevant organic free radical:

Thus the initial rate-limiting step is an electron-transfer from the organic free radical to the permanganate anion:

The reaction,

may not be prominent as reaction (2) is a more favoured one.

The autocatalytic character of the reduction indicates that some active specie is produced in course of the reaction which facilitates the attack on permanganate itself. This active specie, generated in the system, is found to be capable of reducing mercuric chloride and initiating polymerisation, characteristic of free radicals. The Mn(VI), thus formed, may give rise to the reaction sequence (5) to (8):

Step (8) is slow, being through the breaking of the manganic oxalate complex.

The oxalate free radical, thus formed, initiates further reduction by virtue of reaction (3), but it is considerably checked by the loss of the active species in reactions (9) to (12):

4. Cf. Taube, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 1216.

5. *Ibid.*, 1952, **74**, 2769.

Mn(II) is thus produced in the system and this competes for the higher-valent manganese with oxalate (cf. steps 5 to 8) as shown in reactions (14) to (17):

The reactions of the higher-valent manganese with Mn(II) is favoured to that with oxalate anion.

The mechanism leads to the rate expression:

$$\frac{-d(\text{oxidant})}{dt} = k(a-x)(b+x)$$

where 'a' is the initial concentration of the oxidant, 'x' is the concentration of the oxidant reduced, and 'b', the concentration of the inductor. Hence $a-x$ provides the (oxidant) and $b+x$, the $(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{1-})$ at time 't'. This on integration yields:

$$k = \frac{1}{t(a+b)} \log \frac{a(b+x)}{b(a-x)} \quad \dots \quad (a)$$

assuming the rate to be proportional to the concentration of the active specie $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{1-}$. The validity of the rate expression (a) and the experimental finding that Mn(VI) immediately initiates reduction of permanganate by oxalate yield additional evidence in support of this mechanism. This is consistent with the observation of Karla and Ghosh⁶ that Mn(VII) is more effective an inductor than Mn(III) in molecular proportions in the reduction of iodine by oxalate where the induction has been attributed to the role of $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{1-}$, generated by the higher-valent manganese.

The autocatalytic character is due to reaction (13). With the progressive formation of Mn(II) in the reaction, the steps (14) to (16) seem to compete with the steps (5) to (7) and dominate over the latter as is to be understood from the fall in the autocatalytic constants observed. This is to be expected because the domination of reactions (14) to (16) over those of (5 to 7) will result in a fall in the stationary concentration of the active entity, $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{1-}$, for the slow breaking down of the manganic complex (cf. reaction 8).

The rate of dismutation of manganic oxalate complex is high at low oxalate-ion concentration for MnC_2O_4^+ , the most unstable amongst the manganic oxalate complexes being the chief manganic oxalate specie present in the system. This in fact leads to a consequent increase in the stationary concentration of the active entity, $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{1-}$. The autocatalytic character should therefore be more prominent at low oxalate-ion concentration

in accordance with the mechanism advanced here and this is found to be the case. Incidentally, Adler and Noyes⁷ have suggested some intermediate, more efficient than manganous and oxalate ions, in promoting the attack on permanganate and this intermediate appears to be more important when the oxalate-ion concentration is lowered, and this is true here. This mechanism is further in accord with the work of Polissar⁸ on radiochemical exchange.

In a mixture of permanganate and oxalate, presence of bivalent manganese may be important in the initiation of the reduction for its action on MnO_4^{1-} anion and thus be a source of Mn(III) and Mn(VI) , both capable of generating $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{1-}$. Once this radical is made available, the mechanism of further reduction of the oxidant will essentially be the same as the one proposed here.

Towards the end of the reaction, when the reacting system consists of mainly Mn(II) specie of manganese, it obeys a first-order rate law in accordance with the reaction sequence:

where 'n' may be 1, 2 or 3.

For tartrate and citrate, the results are similar and an analogous mechanism is applicable. It may, however, be emphasised that excess of both tartrate and citrate decreases the rate of reduction, as has been found for oxalate. This necessarily leads to the conclusion that either new manganic complexes of these organic anions, tartrate and citrate, appear in the system, and these are more stable, or the disproportionation of these manganic complexes is retarded by excess of the tartrate and citrate. So far only one complex of each tartrate and citrate has, however, been reported.

An interesting feature is the catalytic effect of cobalt(II) on the reduction of permanganate by oxalate, tartrate, and citrate. The permanganate is not reduced by cobalt(II) in aqueous medium or in an acetate-acetic acid mixture at comparable pH.

TABLE III

Specific effect of Co^{2+} ions on the reaction rate.

(Oxalic acid) = $1 \times 10^{-2}N$. (KHCO_3) = $0.7 \times 10^{-2}N$. (Co(II)) = $1 \times 10^{-3}N$.
(KMnO_4) = $1 \times 10^{-3}N$. pH = 4.02 Temp. = 20°.

<i>t</i> (min.)	..	5	10	15	25	35	45	55	65
$k \times 10^4 \text{ sec}^{-1}$	..	1.33	1.34	1.34	1.77	2.04	2.36	3.20	3.89

Even the autocatalytic constants recorded in Table III, have thus a remarkable ascending trend and this is true of tartrate and citrate.

7. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.* 1955, **77**, 2036.

8. *Ibid.*, 1936, **58**, 1372.

A general interpretation of this catalysis may be a slow oxidation of an organic complex of cobalt (II) to Co^{3+} , which prior to the formation of a corresponding complex⁹ of cobalt (III), breaks down, as proposed earlier by us, to give rise to the relevant organic free radical. The above conclusion is substantiated by our observation that potassium cobaltic oxalate does not affect the reduction in dark under the conditions employed here.

Financial assistance from C.S.I.R. is gratefully acknowledged.

DEPARTMENT OF POST-GRADUATE
STUDIES AND RESEARCH IN CHEMISTRY,
UNIVERSITY OF JABALPUR,
JABALPUR.

Received August 7, 1965.

9. Kemp and Waters, *J. Chem. Soc.* 1964, 3193.